

Is the Past Ever Truly Past? The 1970s and the Politics of Time in Turkey

Selin Bengi Gümürükçü

Selin Bengi Gümürükçü is currently a Postdoctoral Associate at the Department of Political Science, Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey in New Brunswick.

As the 45th anniversary of the September 12, 1980 coup in Turkey approaches, the shadows of the military intervention and the preceding period continue to loom over the country's political landscape. The 1980 coup, the third in the history of the republic, represents a pivotal turning point in Turkish politics. Following the institutionalization of right-wing politics in the late 1970s amidst heightened levels of protest and political violence, the coup changed "the political" in the country. The junta that ruled the country for the next three years crushed the leftist movement and shifted the political landscape to the right. More broadly, it also cemented what would become Turkey's dominant political ideology over the ensuing decades – one grounded in a specific form of ethno-religious nationalism – facilitated stealth Islamization (Gumuscu 2024), and reshaped public memory.

Ethno-Religious Nationalism: The Turkish-Islamic Synthesis

Since the late 1960s left-wing students spearheaded protests, demanding greater voice not only in their school administrations but also in the broader decision-making processes in the country, making protest a daily occurrence in Turkey in the late 1960s and 1970s (Gümürükçü 2014). Amid the Cold War, this

rise of leftist youth was perceived by the state as a threat not only to Turkey's territorial integrity but also to its status as the "last surviving Turkish state" (Kenar and Gürpınar 2013). To counter this, right-wing, nationalist students were mobilized, and the clashes between these groups, or between fractions within these groups, escalated into near-civil war after 1973, with daily violent encounters. Parallel to these conflicts, an Islamist movement emerged in the 1970s, reflecting broader regional trends during the Cold War. The wave of Islamism sweeping the Muslim world reshaped Islamist rhetoric in Turkey, influenced by translated works of Hassan al-Banna and Sayyid Qutb (Özkan 2017). The National Turkish Students' Union (*Milli Türk Talebe Birliği*, MTBB) became a hub for Islamist youth during this time, playing a pivotal role, with several founding members of the Justice and Development Party (*Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi*, AKP), including Recep Tayyip Erdoğan, politically socialized within its ranks.

The right-wing and Islamist movements gained traction through institutionalized actors such as political parties, particularly during the two "Nationalist Front" coalition governments, which ruled from March 1975 to June 1977 and from July 1977 to January 1978. These governments expanded religious

education by increasing the number of *İmam Hatip* schools, secondary schools that trained students as imams, with enrollment rising from 35,000 in 1973–74 to 178,000 in 1979–80 (Çakır et al. 2004). They also appointed right-wing academics to key positions in a top-down manner. In 1977, this occurred with Middle East Technical University’s president and board of trustees, sparking protests among students and faculty and a 9-month long boycott of classes. Similar to the ongoing protests at Boğaziçi University that started in 2021 in response to the top-down appointment of a president – a move which overturned the university’s decades-long tradition – these actions underscored state efforts to curtail academic freedom and student activism. The Nationalist Front governments also provided political opportunities and legal protection to far-right nationalist and Islamist groups, whose use of violence escalated under their governance (Gümrükçü 2023).

It was during this time that the MTTB and other organizations organized religious-themed protests, such as Friday prayers in front of Hagia Sophia, advocating its conversion into a mosque (Gümrükçü 2014) – a goal realized by the AKP in 2020. These events also contested secular national history, which does not necessarily make a reference to the Ottoman era, and would even claim a rupture between the Empire and the Republic. By contrast, Islamist organizations led commemorations of Istanbul’s conquest, framing youth as heirs to Fatih Sultan Mehmet’s legacy. This narrative gained further prominence during Erdoğan’s tenure as Istanbul’s mayor in 1994 and under subsequent AKP governments, transforming such events into grand “Conquest Festivals” featuring reenactments, military parades, and light shows (Dissard and Kurşunlugil 2020), serving as ideologically motivated reconstructions of

time.

The right-wing and Islamist movements of the 1970s employed populist and Manichean rhetoric, dismissing leftists as foreign agents and urging them to “leave the country.” Leftist youth were framed as puppets of Moscow or Beijing, juxtaposed against conservatives, who supposedly represented both “local and national” values. This rhetoric reemerged decades later, with the AKP framing opposition groups as suspicious outsiders. This was evident in Erdoğan’s characterization of Gezi Park protesters as *çapulcu* (looters) or as connected to a foreign plot to overthrow the government (Hintz 2016; Gümrükçü 2022).

This period under the Nationalist Front governments marked a shift in power within the military-bureaucratic establishment toward the right. Following the 1980 coup, the junta introduced the “Turkish-Islamic synthesis” (*Türk-İslam Sentezi*), a framework that merged nationalist and Islamist elements to counter “external” ideologies deemed incompatible with Turkey’s identity. Practical measures included making Sunni Islam education compulsory and fostering the visibility of religious groups in politics. The junta’s suppression of the left and promotion of the Turkish-Islamic synthesis consolidated the right’s dominance in Turkish politics.

Collective Memory and Protests

The junta’s constitutional overhaul curtailed civil liberties, muted society, and justified the coup through a narrative of the “dark 1970s,” which portrayed the decade as chaotic and dangerous. This narrative not only suppressed activist knowledge but also fostered a fairly negative perception of street protests. While some activists from the period still organize and/or participate in protests (Gümrükçü

2010; Uysal 2017), the level of mobilization in Turkey remains lower than that observed in Western European countries (Uysal 2006). Events and possibilities of the 1970s were rendered “unthinkable” (Bourdieu 1992) by the coup’s rupture.

The legacy of the “dark 1970s” continues to shape how the current government perceives and suppresses opposition. For example, a now deceased founding member of the AKP argued in 2012 “those engaging in street movements today [in 2012] are aiming for chaos. The military has returned to the barracks, the judiciary has normalized—only the streets remain. They’re calculating whether they can do something to this government through street protests alone” (Başaran 2012). In a similar manner, in response the protests that erupted in March 2025 after the arrest of Istanbul’s mayor, the leader of the Nationalist Action Party blamed the main opposition party for “reopening the dirty pages of history’s dustbin” (Serbestiyet 2015). The Gezi Park protests in 2013 marked a turning point in the suppression of opposition, with the government mobilizing its supporters to defend the state against perceived threats. Since Gezi, mass mobilization in support of autocracy has surpassed democratic mobilization, as seen in the government’s calls for public support during crises, including the failed 2016 coup attempt (Coppedge et al. 2024).

While much of the literature on democratic backsliding in Turkey focuses on recent developments, these developments did not occur in a vacuum. The political struggles of today are echoes of unresolved tensions from the 1970s, making it imperative to revisit how the coup altered Turkey’s trajectory and continues to define its present. The 1980 coup occurred amidst heightened conflict between left- and right-wing actors, representing a

rupture in politics. There is still a lot to be explored regarding lessons derived from the past and their political implications. Examining the institutionalization of right-wing and Islamist politics in the 1970s and the subsequent 1980 coup will encourage social scientists to adopt a more historical approach to understanding democratic erosion, stealth Islamization, as well as more recent protests in Turkey today. ♦

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